

Psychological Methods of Improving the Self-Management of Athletes

Sattorov Mirshod Erkinovich

Researcher at Bukhara State University, Teacher at Bukhara State Pedagogical Institute

Article information:

Manuscript received: 4 Aug 2024; **Accepted:** 10 Sep 2024; **Published:** 28 Oct 2024

Abstract: Self-government plays a key role in the personal development of sports school students, contributing to the formation of independence, responsibility and leadership qualities. This article discusses the research methodology for improving self-government among students of sports schools. The main focus is on methods, approaches and tools that can be used to analyze and assess the level of self-government.

Keywords: Intrinsic motivation, Extrinsic motivation, Goal setting, Self-control, Perseverance, Determination.

METHODS. “Method of regulating one’s own behavior”, chosen based on the goals and objectives of our initial research.

RESULTS. According to the analysis of the results of the first "planning" factor of the methodology, the 8th grade students recorded a high result. Individual characteristics of setting and supporting goals, conscious planning of activities, stability, and independent promotion of activity goals were identified in 8th grade students. In 6th grade students, it was observed that the need for planning in subjects is less developed, goals change frequently, and goals are set depending on the situation.

Introduction. Improving self-government is an important aspect in the training of athletes, as it allows them to develop skills of self-organization and self-control. Sports school students often face high levels of stressful situations and the need to make quick and informed decisions, which makes self-management skills especially important.

Research Methodology

1. Defining the goals and objectives of the study

- Purpose of the study: identifying effective methods and approaches to improving self-government among students in sports schools.
- Research objectives: analyzing the current state of self-government, developing recommendations for its improvement, evaluating the effectiveness of the measures implemented.

2. Research methods

- Questionnaires: conducting surveys among students and coaches to identify the level of self-government and the factors influencing its development.
- Observation: observing students' behavior during training and competitions.

- Interviews: conducting in-depth interviews with students, coaches, and parents to obtain high-quality information about self-government processes.
- Document analysis: studying curricula, training programs, and other documents related to the educational process in sports schools.

3. Conducting the study

- Forming a sample: determining the number and composition of study participants (students of different age groups, coaches, and parents).
- Data collection: conducting questionnaires, observations, and interviews.
- Data processing: using statistical methods to analyze the information obtained.

Results and discussion

As a result of the study, key factors influencing the level of self-government of students in sports schools were identified, and recommendations for its improvement were developed. Among them:

- ✓ Implementation of special trainings and programs aimed at developing leadership qualities and self-government skills.
- ✓ Increasing the role of mentoring and feedback from coaches.
- ✓ Development of a system of incentives and motivating events.

Main psychological aspects of self-government

1. Motivation. Motivation is the driving force of self-government. There are internal and external motivations, which influence students' behavior in different ways. It is important to develop internal motivation, which promotes independence and resistance to external influences.

2. Strong-willed qualities. Will is a person's ability to consciously regulate their activities and overcome difficulties. The development of strong-willed qualities, such as persistence, determination, and self-control, is necessary for effective self-government.

3. Self-esteem. Adequate self-esteem allows students to objectively assess their abilities and achievements, which helps set realistic goals and increase self-confidence.

4. Stress resistance. The ability to manage stress and maintain emotional balance in difficult situations is an important aspect of self-government. This requires relaxation techniques, meditation and other methods of psychological self-regulation.

The forms of self-government in a sports school as an institution of additional education are the pedagogical council, the general meeting of the work collective, the coaching councils of the departments and other forms. In order to practically implement the collegiality of making certain decisions in sports schools, a pedagogical council is created under the chairmanship of the director, which includes deputy directors, senior coaches-teachers, instructors-methodologists, medical workers, representatives of sports organizations and the parent committee. The pedagogical council meets at least once a quarter and discusses the main issues of the school's work, the experience of training young athletes, the results of activities in various areas. Coaching councils are created in the departments for sports, which analyze the training methods, discuss the staffing of teams, etc. Persons who are admitted to teaching activities in a sports school are, as a rule, those who have higher or secondary vocational education and who meet the requirements of the qualification characteristics determined for the relevant positions of teaching staff.

The staffing schedule of a sports school is established by its management independently

depending on the goals and objectives, financial capabilities, taking into account the qualifications of employees (determined on the basis of the tariff and qualification characteristics established for physical education and sports workers, other specialists, employees and workers), as well as the calculation of the number of students who fall into certain stages of training in the current academic year according to their skill level and length of service.

The procedure for recruiting personnel for a sports school is regulated by its charter. The relationship between an employee of a sports school and its administration, regardless of the form of ownership and organizational and legal form, is regulated by an employment contract, the terms of which cannot contradict the labor legislation of the Russian Federation.

Financial management of a sports school. The sports school, being a legal entity, has a current and other accounts in banking institutions, an independent balance sheet, maintains accounting and office work, and provides financial and statistical reporting in accordance with the established procedure. The basis of state guarantees for children of the Russian Federation to receive opportunities to engage in sports in school is state and municipal funding.

The presence of individual characteristics and unique qualities in the pupils of the sports school serves to improve their self-government. As we have already mentioned above, analyzing the indicators of self-government in students of sports schools, paying serious attention to its specific psychological factors is important in ensuring the socio-psychological development of the pupil. From this point of view, in order to have detailed information about flexibility, persistence, endurance and self-control in emotional situations that are typical for students of sports schools, special studies were conducted on the issue of collecting empirical data and the question was raised about the analysis of its results based on socio-psychological requirements. This paragraph is supposed to describe the analysis of empirical data obtained by introducing additional scientific explanations into this issue.

Let us move on to the analysis of the preliminary results obtained using the "Method of regulating one's own behavior", chosen based on the goals and objectives of our initial study.

Xulq-atvorni tartibga solish usuli yordamida olingan dastlabki natijalarni tahlil qilish (n=280)

Factors	Mean (M) differences		Differences
	6th grade n=160	8th grade n=120 t	t
Planning	5,1	7,4	-2,2*
Modeling	6,1	8,6	-2,4*
Programming	5,8	4,9	-1,1
Results evaluation	5,7	8,6	-3,2*
Flexibility	6,4	8,3	-2,4*
Independence	7,1	9,2	-2,2*

Заклучение

If we proceed to the analysis of the preliminary results obtained by the method of "regulating one's own behavior", then reliable differences are observed for a number of factors. Including "planning" ($t = -2.2$; $p < 0.05$), "modeling" ($t = -2.4$; $p < 0.05$), "evaluation of results" ($t = -3.2$; $p < 0.05$) reliable differences were observed in the factors "adaptability" ($t = -2.2$; $p < 0.05$) and "independence" ($t = -2.4$; $p < 0.05$).

The methodology for studying the improvement of self-government in students of sports

schools, presented in this article, allows us to effectively assess the level of self-government and develop measures to improve it. The implementation of the proposed recommendations contributes to the formation of independent, responsible and successful athletes.

To further improve self-government methods, it is recommended to continue research in this area, expanding the samples and applying new approaches to data analysis.

Список литературы

1. Сатторов М. Особенности эмоционального интеллекта спортсменов в индивидуальных и командных видах спорта //Физическое воспитание, спорт и здоровье. – 2020. – №. 1.
2. Условия эффективного повышения уровня физической подготовленности студентов Г.К. Саидов - Nexus: Журнал перспективных инженерных исследований, 2022/12/24
3. Психо-эмоциональные состояния и стрессовой терпимость у спортсменов Г.К. Саидов, Н.С. Ахмедов Образовательные исследования в области универсальных наук 2 (13), 517-520